

PHOTOCONSISTENT AND TRAJECTORY GUIDED NOVEL-VIEW SYNTHESIS TOOL FOR UAV CINEMATOGRAPHY BASED ON AUTOREGRESSIVE TRANSFORMERS

Marco A. Montes-Grova¹, Vasileios Mygdalis², Francisco J. Pérez-Grau¹,
Antidio Viguria¹ and Ioannis Pitas²

¹Advanced Center for Aerospace Technologies (CATEC), Seville, Spain

²Informatics Department, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

Fig. 1: Comparative of results of the proposed tool in different environments. For each environment, the top row shows the ground-truth and the bottom row shows the predicted results using our approach.

ABSTRACT

Novel view synthesis is the task of generating new images that render an object or scene from a different viewpoint than the one given. It aims to create new views of a specific subject starting from a number of pictures taken from a known points of view. The novel view synthesis problem can be approached in two different ways: as a problem of interpolation of images between two known images or extrapolation of images from one or a subset of images. During this work, the problem of the extrapolation will be addressed. Taking advantage of the fact that it is possible to pre-calculate the trajectories that we want the camera that takes the images to execute, from a series of known shot-types. Based on that and on the Autoregressive

Transformers, it is presented a end-to-end tool for novel-view synthesis from previously unvisited points of view for aerial cinematography robots.

Index Terms— Applications of machine learning, Generative AI for Multimedia, UAS Applications

1. INTRODUCTION

The novel view synthesis is a field of study that has grown considerably in recent years. The fields of computer science research, vision research, and artificial intelligence are involved in defining suitable approaches to the problem. The goal is to synthesize a target image with an arbitrary target camera pose from given source images and their camera poses. These synthetic images can be very useful when they come from an aerial robot. The objectives of generating these

This work has received funding from the European Union's European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement AI4Media (951911).

images can be multiple: the capture of photographic reports or the inspection of infrastructures. Although they seem to be very different problems, both have a common denominator which is that a great photoconsistency is needed in the synthesised images. Thus, it is a problem whose solution can be applied to environments as different as those shown in Fig. 1.

The authors of Implicit Multiplane Images (ImMPI) [1] propose a novel view synthesis method for remote sensing. Multiplane images are integrated, which are an explicit form of representation that is inherently well-suited for remote sensing due to recent developments in implicit neural representation. In the proposed method, the 3D scene is constructed under a self-supervised optimization paradigm through a differentiable multiplane renderer with multi-view input constraints.

In [2], a method is presented that autonomously synthesizes a novel perspective by learning to exploit multiple viewpoints. The model is comprised of two modules: one for flow prediction and the other for pixel generation. In order to utilize information directly from source views and to simulate absent pixels from statistical priors, the module for pixel generation is also integrated. To consolidate the forecasts generated by the two modules using multi-view source images, a self-learned confidence aggregation mechanism is implemented.

In [3], a novel fully convolutional network, that can take advantage of the structural information explicitly by incorporating the inverse depth features, is presented. The inverse depth features are obtained from CNNs trained with sparse labeled depth values.

Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF) [4] is a novel viewpoint image generation network that takes a 5D input (x, y, z of spatial coordinate and θ, φ of viewpoint) and outputs volume density (transparency) and radiance (RGB color) released in 2020. NeRF models are used for single-image view synthesis and can generate realistic 3D assets. NeRF models are trained using a large number of input images and their corresponding viewpoints. Basically, NeRF models take a 5D input and output volume density and radiance. Based on NeRF, there are many different implementations of NeRF to solve the problem of novel view synthesis. NeRF architectures are good at interpolating positions between previously visited viewpoints or even locating the camera with respect to the mesh obtained with NeRF from the current image, [5]. Architectures such as F2-NeRF [6] solve the problem of trajectory extrapolation very satisfactorily. However, they regulate the task of extrapolating images from points that have not been previously visited during the training phase.

In summary, this work aims to extrapolate novel views from a series of estimated positions and an input image. Therefore, initially, NeRF-type architectures are not valid since we would need to create a previous mesh to generate these new views. In order to use NeRF architectures to solve our initial problem, we would need to always work in the

same environment. And it would be great to achieve a small degree of generality. An example of using NeRF models to fix localization is done in [7], where the authors patch the image taken by the camera with the one generated by NeRF to correct UAV positions.

In addition, the idea is to work at some point with environments with a certain degree of dynamism, which would make these architectures less effective. However, there is some research on creating NeRF in dynamic environments. Another problem is that NeRF-type architectures are focused on bounded environments. Although there is research on unbounded environments, the initial idea comes from having a bounded environment.

Diffusion models gradually add Gaussian noise through a series of steps into the original image, a process known as diffusion [8]. The goal is to learn a reverse process that slightly denoises the image on the current frame. One advantage of diffusion models is that the training can be done by just picking a random timestamp in the middle for optimization instead of fully reconstructing the image end-to-end.

Diffusion models have a lot of potential [9] [10], but as far as we know, they have only worked in indoor and structured environments, and have not shown their capability in unstructured images. Besides that, it will not generate the same sequence every iteration but will generate a slightly different set of novel views each time the architecture is executed.

A Transformer [11] is a type of neural network architecture used in various fields, including natural language processing, computer vision, and image synthesis. The Transformer model family has inspired many new and exciting models that extend beyond natural language processing tasks. View synthesis is the task of creating new views of a scene from multiple pictures of that scene. [12] Transformers based on autoregressive models, popularized by GPT [13], have shown tremendous success in extrapolating the contents of language models. For image extrapolation, it has demonstrated the same potential.

The main contributions of this work are as follows:

- Trajectory guided novel-view synthesis from unknown poses addressing the image extrapolation problem.
- Open-Source end-to-end tool implemented in ROS for image generation from a known trajectory and an initial image.

The rest of the manuscript is structured as follows: In Section 2, the problem we seek to tackle with this tool is exposed. The proposed tool is developed in Section 3. The different modules will be discussed: how the trajectories are generated, how the data for training is generated, and the architecture of the transformer used. Section 4 details the experimental results of this approach. Finally, in Section 5, a set of conclusions about the tool will be drawn, and the fields of application of this tool will be analyzed.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Hence, the primary goal of this work is the development of a tool for novel view synthesis. This tool will utilize an artificial intelligence system that can create aerial photos from unique perspectives by taking into account the extrinsics and intrinsic camera parameters.

Depending on the pose in space of these new points of view, we can find two different problems: interpolation and extrapolation. This is illustrated in Fig. 2. Assuming the path is followed from right to left, each axis in RGB color is a known viewpoint. To solve the interpolation problem, we would try to generate a novel view from the axis in cyan color. To solve the extrapolation problem, we will try to generate novel views from the magenta axes.

Therefore, during this work, the problem of extrapolating images, or novel views, from known but not previously visited viewpoints will be addressed.

Fig. 2: Illustration of the difference between interpolation and extrapolation problems.

3. PROPOSED TOOL

In Fig. 3 is shown the architecture of the proposed media content creation tool. The proposed tool will take as input the pre-calculated offline path to be executed, as specified in subsection 3.1.

The cinematographic aerial vehicle and its environment will be simulated using the following tools; On the one hand, the environment will be simulated using the 3D computer graphics game engine Unreal Engine 4.27. This allows us to reduce the disparity with reality through its exceptional photorealistic capabilities. On the other hand, to simulate the aerial robot and the mounted camera, from which images of the environment will be taken, we will use AirSim [14], a cross-platform simulator designed for autonomous systems research.

Finally, the main module of the tool is the Autoregressive transformer used to solve the image extrapolation task. For this purpose, an implementation based on GeoGPT [15]. The generation of the synthetic data used to train the model is discussed in 3.2.

This tool has been implemented end-to-end using the ROS (Robot Operative System) framework, [16], in such a way that it can be executed with real data. A complete diagram of the proposed tool is shown in Fig. 3. The open-source implementation of this tool can be found in the following github repository: https://github.com/catec/nvs_trajectory_guided_ros.

3.1. Shot-Type Trajectory Generator

In order to generate the synthesized data and subsequently evaluate the tool, a trajectory generator has been developed based on [17]. This article presents a comprehensive tutorial about developing flight plans for UAVs to achieve autonomous cinematography. To produce trajectories for this tool, the following simplifying assumptions have been made: the target is located at a known position in world coordinates and remains stationary, meaning that its velocity is zero.

Analyzing what UAV shot types are most engaging for the tasks to be solved with the proposed tool, the following have been selected: ORBIT, FLYBY, and FLYOVER. The notation used in the article and, by extension, the notation used in this work is as follows:

The WCS is a fixed, orthonormal, right-handed World Coordinate System, with its k -axis vertical to a local tangent plane (hereafter shortened to “ground plane”). For instance, a local East-North-Up (ENU) coordinate system may be employed. The TCS is the current, orthonormal, right-handed Target-centered Coordinate System. Its origin lies on the current target position, its k -axis is vertical to the ground plane, and its i -axis is the \mathcal{L}_2 -normalized projection of the current target velocity vector onto the ground plane.

At time instant t ; $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t$ is the 3D UAV position in WCS, \mathbf{x}_t is the 3D UAV position in TCS, $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}_t$ is the 3D UAV velocity in WCS, \mathbf{v}_t is the 3D UAV velocity in TCS, $\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_t$ is the 3D target position in WCS, \mathbf{p}_t is the 3D target position in TCS and \mathbf{l}_t is the 3D position at which the camera looks (known as “Look At Point”) in TCS.

It should be noted that, in order to generalise these trajectories, it is necessary after calculation to transform positions and velocities to the world reference frame, WCS.

3.1.1. ORBIT

The parameters that must be specified are the desired 3D Euclidean distance $\lambda_{3D} = \|\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t - \tilde{\mathbf{p}}_t\|_2 = \|\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t\|_2$ (constant over time), the angle of the entire rotation to be performed around the target (θ) and the desired UAV angular velocity w . Additionally, we can easily derive the initial angle θ_0 formed by the TCS i -axis (of time instance 0) and the vector from \mathbf{p}_0 to the projection of the known initial position \mathbf{x}_0 onto the TCS ij -plane. Then, ORBIT may be described in TCS using a planar circular motion:

Fig. 3: Diagram of the architecture of the proposed tool. It can be seen that in order to be able to use it, it is necessary to calculate the desired trajectory offline. After that, the image at the time instant t and the N positions from which the new viewpoints are to be generated will be taken as input. As output, it will generate the N synthesised novel views.

$$\begin{aligned}
 t &\in \left[0, \frac{T\theta}{\omega}\right]; & \theta_0 &= \arctan\left(\frac{x_{02}}{x_{01}}\right) \\
 x_{t3} &= x_{03}, \forall t \\
 \lambda &= \sqrt{\lambda_{3D}^2 - x_{t3}^2} \\
 \mathbf{x}_t &= \left[\lambda \cos\left(t\frac{\omega}{T} + \theta_0\right), \lambda \sin\left(t\frac{\omega}{T} + \theta_0\right), x_{t3} \right]^T \\
 \mathbf{l}_t &= \mathbf{p}_t
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

3.1.2. FLYBY and FLYOVER

The common parameter that must be specified is K , i.e., the time (in seconds) until the UAV is located exactly above the target (for FLYOVER) or until the distance vector between the target and the UAV is minimized in Euclidean norm (for FLYBY). Additionally, d , i.e., the length of the projection of that minimal distance vector onto the ground plane, must be specified for FLYBY. Below, the target velocity is assumed constant for reasons of modeling convenience. The base mathematical description common to both trajectories is the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{v}_0 &= \left[\frac{u_{01}K - x_{01}}{K}, 0, u_{03} \right]^T \\
 \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_t &= \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_{t-1}, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_t = \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{t-1}, \forall t \\
 \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t &= \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0 + \frac{t}{KT} (\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{KT} - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) \\
 [\tilde{u}_{t1}, \tilde{u}_{t2}, 0]^T \times [\tilde{v}_{t1}, \tilde{v}_{t2}, 0]^T &\approx \mathbf{0} \\
 \mathbf{l}_t &= \mathbf{p}_t, \quad t \in [0, 2KT]
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Additionally, the following holds for FLYOVER:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{KT} &= [\tilde{p}_{01} + \tilde{u}_{01}K, \tilde{p}_{02} + \tilde{u}_{02}K, \tilde{x}_{03} + \tilde{u}_{03}K]^T \\
 x_{t2} &\approx 0, \quad \mathbf{x}_t^T \mathbf{j} \approx 0, \forall t
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

and the following holds for FLYBY:

$$\begin{aligned}
 |x_{02}| &= d > 0 \\
 x_{t2} &= x_{02}, \forall t \\
 \mathbf{x}_{KT} &= [0, x_{02}, x_{03}]^T
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

3.2. Synthetic Data Generation

As mentioned above, in order to evaluate the developed tool, we have chosen to create different simulation environments in Unreal Engine 4.27. This shows the usefulness of the proposed tool in different use cases. In particular, we want to assess the applicability to use cases of visual inspection of industrial environments and generation of media content of monuments.

The simulation of the Cinematographic Aerial Robot will be done through AirSim. This framework allows us to simulate an ideal motion model of a quadrotor as well as a series of on-board sensors. In this case, only an RGB camera will be simulated, and a gimbal that allows it to be oriented in the required direction.

Therefore, through AirSim, we can control the position and orientation of the UAV and the orientation of the onboard gimbal, and simulate a camera to capture images of the simulated environment. An example of the simulated environments and images taken from it is shown in Fig. 4.

3.3. GeoGPT Transformer

Taking as input the current camera image of the simulated aerial robot and the positions and the following N positions and orientations of the trajectory being executed. It will generate as output N novel views of the simulated environment. In this autoregressive transformer architecture, a modified self-attention block, has been added in which the camera position is taken into account to generate the novel view. The architecture has been trained with almost all default parameters. Only the number of transformer layers has been decreased to 16 in order to speed up the training and decrease the memory consumption. It has been verified that this does not affect the performance of the tool.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In order to evaluate the performance of the tool, we will analyze how much visual consistency is lost when generating

Fig. 4: Example of the synthetic data generated through Unreal Engine and AirSim.

novel views. Therefore, the spacing between viewpoints will be taken as the variable to be modified. One image per second will be taken at each position; therefore, the gap between positions is directly related to the speed of the aircraft. In other words, the aim is to evaluate at what speed the simulated aerial robot can take (or generate) images without losing visual consistency.

A number of variables, like the trajectory or the scenario, must be set. The ORBIT trajectory was chosen as the evaluation’s trajectory, and the monumental scenario was determined to be used. In addition, the number of novel views to be generated will be set to 5.

A total dataset of around 4.000 images with all their associated poses in WCS has been created at minimum speed, i.e. one image per second. The images have been generated from pre-calculated trajectories around the central target of the environment. The variable parameter of the shot type ORBIT, the Euclidean distance to the target λ_{3D} , has been randomised within a valid evaluation threshold. The randomization of the inter-image spacing is managed implicitly in the manner in which GeoGPT imports the data during training. The model has been trained on a workstation with 4 RTX1080 12 GB and 128 GB RAM for approximately 12 hours.

Regarding the metrics used to assess the consistency of the novel views, the same metrics will be used as in the original GeoGPT work. Two metrics will be used: LPIPS, [18] and PSNR. LPIPS measures the perceptual similarity in deep feature space, and PSNR measures pixel-wise differences between two images. Therefore, a series of images with different gap sizes between them has been generated to evaluate the tool’s performance.

Fig. 5: Comparison between prediction and ground truth with different gaps length.

	Gap 5	Gap 15	Gap 25	Gap 35
PSNR (\uparrow)	23.05	21.84	18.51	17.32
LPIPS (\downarrow)	1.8726	2.2412	2.7132	2.9870

Table 1: Metrics comparison based on viewpoints spacing

Fig. 5 shows the results obtained with each evaluated configuration. As can be seen, the consistency of the images is good when the gap is small, which is analogous to the UAV moving at a very low speed. However, when the gap is around 25 positions between viewpoints, it is observed how, from the second image, there begins to be a notable offset between the predictions and the ground truth. Finally, in the most extreme case, which implies that the aircraft moves at high speed, only the first generated image is consistent, with the rest having a considerable visual difference from the ground truth.

5. CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we have presented an end-to-end tool for generating novel views from unvisited points of view. Future improvements for the tool include replacing GeoGPT with a diffusion model, which would learn the environment more consistently. Another improvement could be to modify Autoregressive Transformer to learn the camera movement and give as input only the current image and desired shot type.

Although only simulation results have been presented with a very restricted evaluation range, the potential that this

type of tool could have for aerial robots has been presented. This could have a wide range of applications in different use cases, including but not limited to the following.

Completion of aerial footage or visual inspection: If the desired trajectory has not been completed, this tool can be used to synthesize the remaining images at low speed.

Vision-Based Trajectory Optimization: Assuming the novel views from the tool as the ground truth of a perfect trajectory and taking as input the current image of the UAV, we can estimate different types of errors. On one hand, the error in the image plane could be estimated in such a way that control architectures based on visual servoing could be implemented. On the other hand, by making use of some other Deep Learning architecture [19], it is possible to obtain a position error in WCS coordinates that would allow the feedback of aerial robot controllers in GNSS-Denied environments.

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